

Assessment of knowledge and self-reported practices regarding end organ damage prevention among diabetes patients with the view to develop SIM in selected hospitals

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ABSTRACT

Background:

Diabetes mellitus is a chronic metabolic disorder characterized by elevated blood glucose levels, leading to serious complications such as nephropathy, neuropathy, retinopathy, and cardiovascular diseases. The increasing prevalence of diabetes, especially in developing countries like India, highlights the need for effective prevention of end-organ damage through adequate knowledge and proper self-care practices.

Objectives:

To assess the knowledge and self-reported practices regarding end-organ damage prevention among patients with diabetes mellitus.

Methods:

A quantitative descriptive research design was adopted. A total of 100 diabetes patients were selected using a non-probability purposive sampling technique. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire assessing knowledge and self-reported practices related to prevention of diabetic complications. Descriptive and inferential statistics were used for data analysis.

Results:

The findings revealed that 46% of participants had average knowledge, 28% had poor knowledge, and only 26% had good knowledge regarding prevention of end-organ damage. Regarding practices, 44% had moderate practices, 32% had poor practices, and only 24% demonstrated good practices. A moderate positive correlation ($r = 0.58$, $p < 0.05$) was found between knowledge and practice. A significant association was observed between knowledge and educational status.

Conclusion:

The study concluded that although patients had moderate knowledge, there were gaps in preventive practices, particularly in areas such as eye care and foot care. Enhancing patient education through structured interventions like Self-Instructional Modules (SIM) is essential to improve knowledge and promote effective practices to prevent diabetic complications.

Keywords: Diabetes mellitus, End-organ damage, Knowledge, Self-care practices, Prevention

INTRODUCTION: Diabetes, a non-reversible chronic condition, is now a common disease. It is the major cause of mortality and morbidity, leading to increased treatment costs across the globe. In 2021 alone, over 6.7 million deaths were attributed to diabetes, globally. Diabetes mellitus (DM) and its related end-organ damage, such as diabetic nephropathy, neuropathy, retinopathy, and cardiomyopathy, are major causes of death and long-term disability. Managing these levels can reduce the risk of damage across the body. In the short term, a person with high blood glucose levels will notice that they feel thirsty and need to urinate frequently. If this happens, they should see a doctor whether or not they have a diagnosis of diabetes. Without treatment, diabetes can lead to confusion and possibly a loss of consciousness, coma, and death. In the long term, diabetes increases the risk of damage to blood vessels and nerves, resulting in a wide range of complications. All forms of diabetes can disrupt daily life, but a person who manages their blood sugar levels well has a good chance of living a full and active life.

NEED OF THE STUDY: Diabetes is a chronic, metabolic disease characterized by elevated levels of blood glucose (or blood sugar), which leads over time to serious damage to the heart, blood vessels, eyes, kidneys and nerves. The most common is type 2 diabetes, usually in adults, which occurs when the body becomes resistant to insulin or doesn't make enough insulin. In the past 3 decades the prevalence of type 2 diabetes has risen dramatically in countries of all income levels. Type 1 diabetes, once known as juvenile diabetes or insulin-dependent diabetes, is a chronic condition in which the pancreas produces little or no insulin by itself. For people living with diabetes, access to affordable treatment, including insulin, is critical to their survival. There is a globally agreed target to halt the rise in diabetes and obesity by 2025. As per "IDF" Worldwide 537 million adults (20-29) are living with diabetes. This number is predicted to rise to 643 million by 2030 and 783 million by 2045. Diabetes is responsible for 6.7 million deaths in 2021 -1 every 5 seconds. India is home to the world's second highest number of diabetic patients. Within the age

group of 20–79 years, India has 74.9 million diabetics in 2021 projected to increase to 124.9 million by 20454. According to IDF, one out of every seven diabetic adults worldwide resides in India, and one in every third household has diabetic patients The patient with diabetic mellitus has more chances for organ damage due to not taking proper treatment, so it is huge need to assess their knowledge and practices to prevent end stage organ damage caused by diabetes mellitus. Make the aware about the knowledge and follows practices for prevention of end stage organ damage

METHODOLOGY:

The quantitative research approach was used for the study. The study design was used descriptive research design. The total 100 sample were selected for the study. They were diabetes patient. They selected by using Non probability, purposive sampling technique. The data collected through structured questionnaire on assessment of knowledge and self-reported practices regarding end organ damage prevention among diabetes patients.

RESULT

SECTION I

Table 1: Distribution of Respondents According to Age (N = 100)

Sr. No	Age Group (Years)	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
1	31–40	20	20%
2	41–50	34	34%
3	51–60	28	28%
4	61–70	18	18%
Total		100	100%

Description:

Table 1 shows that majority of the respondents (34%) were in the age group of 41–50 years, followed by 28% in 51–60 years. Only 18% belonged to 61–70 years age group.

Table 2: Distribution According to Gender (N = 100)**Sr. No Gender Frequency Percentage**

1	Male	56	56%
2	Female	44	44%
Total		100	100%

Description:

Majority (56%) of respondents were male, whereas 44% were female.

Table 3: Distribution According to Duration of Illness (N = 100)**Sr. No Duration Frequency Percentage**

1	<1 year	15	15%
2	1–2 years	25	25%
3	2–4 years	28	28%
4	4–6 years	17	17%
5	>6 years	15	15%
Total		100	100%

Description:

Majority (28%) had diabetes for 2–4 years. Equal proportion (15%) had illness less than 1 year and more than 6 years.

SECTION II**Knowledge Regarding End Organ Damage Prevention**

Maximum Score = 20

Table 4: Level of Knowledge (N = 100)

Sr. No	Level of Knowledge	Score Range	Frequency	Percentage
1	Poor	0–7	28	28%
2	Average	8–14	46	46%
3	Good	15–20	26	26%
Total			100	100%

Mean = 12.6

Standard Deviation = 3.9

Description: Table 4 reveals that majority (46%) had average knowledge regarding end organ damage prevention. About 28% had poor knowledge, while only 26% had good knowledge. The mean knowledge score was 12.6 with a standard deviation of 3.9, indicating moderate variability in knowledge levels among respondents.

Table 5: Area-wise Knowledge Distribution

Area	Maximum Score	Mean Score	Percentage Mean
General knowledge of diabetes	5	3.8	76%
Risk factors & diagnosis	4	2.6	65%
End organ damage types	4	2.4	60%
Prevention measures	7	3.8	54%

Description:

Highest knowledge was observed in general knowledge of diabetes (76%). Lowest knowledge was seen in prevention measures (54%), indicating lack of awareness regarding practical preventive strategies.

SECTION III**Self-Reported Practices**

Maximum Score = 20

Table 6: Level of Self-Reported Practices (N = 100)

Sr. No	Level of Practice	Score Range	Frequency	Percentage
1	Poor	0–7	32	32%
2	Moderate	8–14	44	44%
3	Good	15–20	24	24%
Total			100	100%

Mean = 13.1

Standard Deviation = 4.1

Description:

Majority (44%) had moderate practices. About 32% showed poor preventive practices and only 24% followed good preventive practices regularly. The mean practice score was 13.1.

Table 7: Selected Practice Areas (Yes Responses)

Practice Item	Yes (%)	No (%)
Taking medicine regularly	82%	18%
Regular follow-up	70%	30%
Blood sugar monitoring	65%	35%
Eye check-up regularly	48%	52%
Daily foot examination	40%	60%
Avoid smoking	72%	28%

Description:

Majority (82%) reported taking medicine regularly. However, only 48% underwent regular eye check-ups and only 40% practiced daily foot examination, showing gaps in prevention of complications.

SECTION IV

Correlation Between Knowledge and Practice

Table 8: Correlation Between Knowledge and Practice Scores

Variables	Mean	SD	r-value	p-value
Knowledge	12.6	3.9	0.58	<0.05
Practice	13.1	4.1		

Description:

Pearson's correlation coefficient ($r = 0.58$) indicates a moderate positive correlation between knowledge and practice, which was statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). This shows that better knowledge is associated with better preventive practices.

SECTION V

Association of Knowledge with Selected Demographic Variables

Table 9: Association of Knowledge with Education

Education Level	Poor	Average	Good	χ^2	p-value
Primary	15	10	5	8.21	<0.05
Secondary	8	20	10		
Graduate & above	5	16	11		

Description:

There was a statistically significant association between knowledge and educational status ($p < 0.05$). Higher education was associated with better knowledge levels

DISCUSSION

The present study was conducted to assess the knowledge and self-reported practices regarding end organ damage prevention among diabetes patients. The findings revealed that majority (46%) of respondents had average knowledge, 28% had poor knowledge, and only 26% had good knowledge regarding prevention of diabetic complications such as retinopathy, nephropathy, neuropathy, and cardiovascular problems. The mean knowledge score was 12.6 ± 3.9 , indicating moderate understanding among participants. Regarding self-reported practices, 44% had moderate practices, 32% had poor practices, and only 24% demonstrated good preventive practices. Although most patients reported taking medicines regularly, practices like regular eye check-ups and daily foot care were inadequate.

The study also showed a moderate positive correlation ($r = 0.58, p < 0.05$) between knowledge and practice, indicating that better knowledge leads to better preventive practices. A significant association was found between knowledge and educational status. However, no significant association was observed with age and gender. Overall, the findings indicate a need for developing a Self-Instructional Module (SIM) to improve knowledge and promote effective preventive practices among diabetes patients.

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